

NAMING OF THE “AGE” CONCEPT

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Abstract. This article covers a wide range of theoretical and practical ideas and attitudes expressed in the analysis of works devoted to the study of age and age-related periods.

Key words and expressions: analyzing, the periods, youth, the interpretation, conclusions, languages, semantic, human age, names, growth, growth, people, the silence, the expressions, the conceptual, indicated.

НАЗВАНИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ «ВОЗРАСТ»

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается широкий спектр теоретических и практических идей и установок, высказанных при анализе работ, посвященных изучению возраста и возрастных периодов.

Ключевые слова и выражения: анализ, периоды, молодость, интерпретация, выводы, языки, семантика, возраст человека, имена, рост, люди, молчание, выражения, понятийное, указанное.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of analyzing the work devoted to the study of the periods of “youth” and “age”, we observed that there are many theoretical and practical views and attitudes to this problem. Let us now turn to the interpretation of scientific research.

In French, the concept of ‘young’ is verbalized by the lexeme ‘âge’. This sound complex in its present form was first recorded in writing during the medieval French period. According to etymological dictionaries, the word “âge” (young) originated from the ancient French language in the XI century, probably in the form of *âage*, *eäge*.

As mentioned earlier, the French word ‘âge’ (young) is derived from the classical Latin word *ætās*, meaning ‘longevity’, and the much earlier form of the popular Latin *ætaticum*, which is based on phonetic laws. The classical *ætās*, on the other hand, goes back to the earlier approximate form *ævitas* with *ævus*, which means “infinity, eternity, duration, distance.”

The first note in the *eäge* form of the word belongs to the 1080 Song of Roland (Chanson de Rolland). The *âage* form was recorded in the twelfth century and lasted until the sixteenth century. Then, as a result of phonetic changes, by the seventeenth century the word was in the form of *âge*, which still exists today.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

According to written sources, the historical evolution of the meaning of a word, that is, its filling with content, is also known. In 1100, the meaning of “human life taken at all distances” was recorded (Chanson de Rolland). In 1160 - “the time since the birth of man” (in the works of Wace, Roman de Rou, Chrét de Troyes, Chevalier au Lyon). In 1188 only *âge adulte*, *majorité* - adulthood, puberty, puberty, puberty (Partonopeus de Blois), then (in 1260) *âge mûr* - puberty, puberty, puberty (Ph. De Novare, Quatre âges) de l'Homme). In 1267, by analogy with the period of human life, the meaning of the “historical” period appears. [2]

It is clear from this fact that the concept of 'age' in its early stages of understanding is equated with the concept of 'time', which is conceived in the French worldview as a representation of all life span, length and even eternity.

Taking into account the opinion of scientists and the fact that the vast majority of linguistic units meaning "young" were created by peoples - linguists without scientific knowledge about specific periods of human life, based on the semantics of the studied language units, we distinguish the following lexical-semantic groups:

1. Phrase-semantic groups meaning "childhood" and lexical units related to the description of adolescence;
2. Lexical-semantic groups with the meaning of "adolescence";
3. Lexical-semantic groups meaning "age of maturity", which includes linguistic units representing the age of maturity and maturity or the first and second periods of maturity age;
4. In lexical-semantic groups meaning "old age", because, firstly, there is a very limited number of language units representing "old age", and secondly, in some cases the semantics of language units simultaneously "old age" and "old age" can express concepts;
5. Generalized "young" semantic lexical-semantic groups. This lexical-semantic group includes lexemes and phraseologies that combine the two consecutive "young periods" in the "young" cycle of life, which are related to the notion of "age" in general, as opposed to old age and youth, as many human-related phenomena, often belong to complex and ambiguous groups that are not subject to rigorous and precise mathematical analysis.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before proceeding directly to the analysis of each of the lexical-semantic groups highlighted, we will show that each of them includes both word-structured and sentence-structural units (proverbs, parables).

L.I. Sidorova draws attention to the fact that the English semantic words "gender" and "young" are associated with the problem of coexistence. In choosing the lexical material, the author considers it necessary: a) to take into account the presence of special markers in dictionaries (of a man, of a woman, of a child, female, male); b) to take into account the words in the form; c) component analysis of English interpretations and Russian correspondences of the studied lexemes; g) to analyze the possibility of combining lexemes in dictionary articles that do not have the appropriate markers, but are personal names of the person.

The researcher believes that the "young" component often accompanies the "gender" component and is represented in the structure of the lexical meaning by the semantics "adult" / "immature" ("very young"): girl - adult girl (gender + height) not reached); rich - child (male + juvenile)

90% of the material analyzed by the author of the article (meaning 1000 lexemes containing the components "gender" and "age") consisted of horses. According to the researcher, the semantics "male" and "female", "adult" and "immature" are combined with more subject and person categorical semantics than character and action categorical semantics.[4]

E.I. Bondarenko in Russian, the sign of old age is "pojiloy" (old age, aging, aging), "postarevshiy" (old, aging), "starenkiy" (old, aging), "stoletniy" (lived a hundred years, face) can be given by the adjectives, one hundred years old, one hundred years old) helpless, helpless, helpless, trembling, trembling, etc.) studies the peculiarities of the use of words, as well as the

linguistic possibilities of the nomination in Russian: "Russian" old man, "old man", "grandfather, grandfather" in English "old man"; "old woman, old woman", "grandmother, aunt" - "old woman", "wife, happy wife" - "little woman"... " indicates[5]

Expression of gender and age in Mordovian zoonyms ”in the article V.A. Ryabova analyzes the methods of expressing the sex and age of living things in Finno-Ugric languages. The abbreviations used by the author in the article indicate the type of Mordovian group language: m.- Mokshan language, md.-Mordovian language, e.-Erzyan language. There are several ways to express the age characteristics of animals and birds: 1. There are two ways to express the age of young livestock: a) lexical: in the Mordovian language "vaz" - "calf"; "vasho" in Erzyan, "vasha" in Mokshan - "toycha, toy"; b) syntactically, where the corresponding name is given postpositively (after a directly related word or part of speech) in Erzyan with the word "levks", in Mokshan with the word "lefks" "detyonysh, ptenchik" child, chicken); Erzyan language "reve levks", Mokshan language "ucha lefks" - "yagnyonok" (lamb); Erzyan language "tuvo levks", Mokshan language "tuva lefks" - "porosyonok" (piglet).

2. Adults can be limited in age by the Mordovian word "od" - "young" (young) and the Erzyan language "syre", the Mokshan language "sire" - "old" (old), for example: in the Erzyan language "od skal" , in Mokshan «od trax» - «young cow» (young cow, heifer), in Mordovian «od saraz» - «young chicken» (young chicken); "sire skal" in Erzyan, "sire trax" in Mokshan - "staraya korova" (old cow).

In limiting the age of domestic animals and birds, as well as in Erzyan "veyske isn", in Mokshan "fkya kizon" - "odnogodovalyy" (one year old), in Erzyan "kavto yen", in Mokshan "kafta kizon" - "dvukhgodovalyy" (two years old)) such as limiting lexemes (compounds) may also be used [6]

G.V. Lyubimova systematizes the peculiarities of the young names of the population of Western Siberia. Children were usually characterized by compound terms that characterized their neck and demeanor: meloch, bez godkov, cherevo, papolza, lopotun. It is noted that because of the abstraction of the position of babies, they are called by terms that mean "baby, child", as well as "raw, poorly baked bread" ("kuvyatka / kuvyaka").

The researcher focuses on important evidence. "A newborn child was not considered a human being until a series of religious ceremonies were performed; "Any child is born 'raw 'and the ' re-cooking 'of rituals that believe' needs to be finished '... is aimed at separating the child from the ' alien '(natural, inhuman) circle and adding it to the ' own '(cultural, human) circle. was "[7]

The author of the article cites interesting information: "with the pagan shade (nextrist) the ethnic name of the neighboring people could often be used as a term of age; as an example, in the land of Narim it was called 'tatarin' until the infant was baptized. The term "saryn", which is used in the form of a word to insult children, meaning "arbitrary" and "Malay", had a tendency to discriminate against children. As a word related to adolescence, terms derived from natural (plant and animal) concepts were used: "nedorostysh" - "short man, animal or plant", "nedorostik" - a minor boy, "nedoroslenka" - "girl"; The word 'meluzga' meant 'small fish' and 'children'; The word 'zuyok' means 'bird of the breed of fishing birds' and 'juvenile, helper on a hunting boat; The word "roshcha" meant "teenagers of both sexes," "rural youth of different ages," and the word "verba" meant "beautiful, beautiful."

The researcher makes an analogy with the terms related to bread and human life: “The term ‘mature, baked’ (similar to the term ‘baby’, ‘raw, unbaked bread’) used to refer to grown girls is an example of equating the stages of human growth and baking in the worldview. , in this case, "readiness to marry"

According to the author, the most archaic layers of youth terminology and folk culture, in general, include plant and ornithomorphic symbols: and the family was preserved in the image of women, while the motif associated with the religious rite of fertility prayer came to the fore.

The article examines the etymology and specific methods of use of words and analyzes the terminology related to middle age and old age. The author notes that the concept of ‘old, old man’ was, for a traditional society, ‘not just an age category, a life cycle, a stage, it expressed a specific social role’. In Siberia, the names of the sex-"youth" period often contained archaic notions about the religious duties of the group being represented, and the concept of "age" itself meant not only a quantitative expression of years lived, but also a certain state of physical, mental, and spiritual status.»

CONCLUSION

D.Katskova makes an interesting observation in her work on a complex comparative analysis of the nomenclature of "age" in Russian and Slovak. According to the researcher, in the nomination on the sign of age, derived from the periods of human life, the difference between the Russian and Slovak languages is reflected in the background of typological similarities that reflect the interlinguistic need. The difference is that "for the Slovak language the principle of onomasiological (primitive) diversity, and in the Russian language - the suffix diversity is the main [8]

In Russian, there are no linguistic equivalents to Slovak names for children in infancy, and in Slovak, there are no adequate equivalents of suffixes common in Russian, such as "malchishechka, malchonka, malchugan", and the Slovak name primarily characterizes the object of terms. and the horse denotes the emotional-evaluative relationship of the object being named.

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